

World Safety Journal

A peer-reviewed journal,
published by the World Safety Organization

Journal Homepage:
<https://worldsafety.org/wso-world-safety-journal/>

The integration of behavior-based safety (BBS) as a company value is advocated!

Harbans Lal^{1*} and E.M. Choueiri²

¹ Professor of Psychology (Retd.), SNTD Women's University;
Director, Forum of Behavioural Safety, Mumbai, India

² WSO Board Member and Liaison Officer to the United Nations;
Professor at several Lebanese universities

KEYWORDS

BBS
Micro
Macro
Components
Pros
Cons
Effectiveness

ABSTRACT

Nearly all cases involving dangerous substances involve human error. Human error caused several disasters, including Bhopal and Chernobyl. The Health and Safety Executive (2023) states that human error management must be as rigorous as technical and engineering processes to prevent accidents and diseases. Human factors—positive or negative—influence employee behavior in a firm. Positive variables can improve safety culture, while reactive variables can hurt it. Restoring a strong safety culture depends on how top executives handle safety problems. A comprehensive safety culture framework integrates information from many conceptualizations to show how safety culture evolves and what variables influence it. This article summarizes qualitative or informal organizational behavior-based safety (BBS) deployment.

1. INTRODUCTION

An analysis of incidents and accidents indicates that human error is a contributing factor in nearly all instances involving exposure to hazardous substances. The primary factor behind numerous catastrophic incidents, such as those that occurred at Bhopal and Chernobyl, was attributed to human error. According to the Health and Safety Executive (2023), the efficacy of human error or mistake management is contingent upon its robustness being on par with the technical and engineering protocols implemented to avert accidents and illnesses. Human factors, whether negative or positive, refer to the elements within an organizational setting that impact the attitudes and conduct of employees. Positive variables have the potential to enhance the safety culture, whereas reactive variables may have a detrimental effect on it.

Lal (2023) posits that various factors such as limited time, fear, and inadequate resources can contribute to a mindset where safety decisions are not prioritized, safety culture is downplayed, and accidents gradually accrue, resulting in detrimental effects on individuals and assets. The response of top-level executives to safety-related incidents is considered a crucial determinant in reinstating a robust safety culture. Health, Safety, and Environment (HSE) experts emphasize the significance of

* Corresponding Author: kailahl@hotmail.com

maintaining equilibrium between challenges and concerns when incorporating behavior-based safety (BBS) and promoting a sound safety ethos.

2. BACKGROUND

BBS is a proactive method for encouraging safe behavior in a specific area. BBS is concerned with lowering dangers, risks, and events by observing a person's behavior and identifying what happens when that behavior occurs. It entails assessing the implications of a certain behavior and providing appropriate reinforcement for the desired behavior. BBS is dependent on total trust and collaboration between managers and employees. BBS is significant because it provides long-term solutions for risk and hazard elimination. This life-saving method promotes a safety culture in the workplace, which is critical for long-term success. According to the Health and Safety Authority (HSA), organizations strive to build a holistic safety culture within their area of responsibility. This is accomplished when each employee regards safety as a value and ensures the safety of coworkers. The BBS strategy is all about reducing risky behaviors and continuously improving safety performance (Safety Culture, 2023).

The micro-BBS strategy seeks to modify employee behavior in order to increase workplace safety. The behavioral safety procedure comprises the following seven steps:

- An identification of potentially problematic behaviors, such as hazardous or risky ones.
- A determination of the underlying causes of the observed behaviors.
- A creation of potential corrective measures.
- An assessment of corrective measures.
- A creation of the processes required to execute the BBS program.
- An execution of the BBS program.
- An evaluation of the BBS program's collected data to determine if it addressed the problem or increased safe behavior.

The macro-BBS approach seeks to effect lasting cultural change within an organization. This is the culture of safety that the majority of organizations strive to accomplish through their safety programs. Michael Topf designed a six-step procedure for achieving this long-term workplace safety solution. The six stages are as follows:

- Assess and analyze the workplace culture.
- Teach and instruct every employee about behavior-based workplace safety.
- Encourage the participation of all employees in the BBS program.
- Strengthen consciousness, accountability, self-observation, and self-management.
- Continuously support and dedicate oneself to employees.
- Provide evaluation and feedback.

Three factors—internal personal factors, external environmental factors, and behavior factors—reflect a complete safety culture, according to Geller (Safety Culture, 2023). These conditions must exist at all times. The integrated approach is fundamental to BBS and is founded on Geller's seven principles. This integrated approach employs both individual and organizational behavior to achieve a culture of total safety. Here are the seven principles:

- The behavior modification techniques should be observable.
- External factors that can aid in the comprehension and improvement of behavior should be determined.

- Antecedents should be utilized to direct behavior, whereas consequences should be utilized to motivate behavior.
- Positive outcomes to reinforce desirable conduct should be highlighted.
- An objective and measurable BBS program should be ensured.
- Hypotheses and combined BBS program data should be generated, in order not to limit the possibilities.
- A BBS program that takes into account the emotions and attitudes of employees should be created.

3. COMPONENTS OF THE BBS PROGRAM

The essential components of a BBS program for effective implementation are as follows (Safety Culture, 2023):

- **Standards for conduct and performance**, including the vision, mission, priorities, policies, processes, and methods, as well as everything else involved, must be communicated to all program participants.
- **Physical resources**, which consist of the tools, equipment, funds, and facilities that are required to implement a BBS system, while psychosocial resources include time, training, culture, and leadership.
- **A system of measurement** that ensures that behavioral observations are quantifiable by establishing criteria for evaluating performances and providing objective feedback.
- **Effective consequences** that can increase positive behavior. Positive reinforcements are one type of effective consequences.
- **Appropriate application**: The system must be equitable; in other words, it provides recognition and rewards when appropriate.
- **A continuous evaluation of the BBS program** enables the program to be continuously enhanced; this will also determine the effectiveness of the program.

The interdependence of work and safety implies that establishing and maintaining a safety culture requires a deliberate attention to multiple levels of impact on employee safety and welfare. Integrated interventions that are effective exhibit key attributes such as the development of interventions, their implementation, and the resultant outcomes.

4. ADVANTAGES AND DISADVANTAGES OF THE BBS SYSTEM

The following are some pros and cons of a BBS approach (Gould, 2019):

Pros:

- BBS programs encourage employee participation. BBS is advantageous in that it encourages the participation of all employees. The program attempts to provide a clear picture of what is working and what is not in terms of safety. In fact, a genuine BBS program cannot function without the participation and involvement of all employee levels.
- BBS programs utilize positive reinforcement. Regarding workplace safety, a small amount of optimism can go a long way. Workplace "safety" is not everyone's favorite topic. The majority of employees detest training sessions and safety meetings. Putting a positive spin on safety can enhance the workplace's overall safety culture.

Cons:

- BBS programs are challenging to maintain. To be effective, a BBS program requires the complete support of senior management. It must also be utilized and evaluated frequently. BBS will be ineffective if it is merely "implemented" without structure, commitment, and follow-up.
- Inadvertently, BBS programs assign "blame" to employees. Although assigning "blame" to employees is not the goal of a genuine BBS program, it is difficult to isolate its effects. After all, BBS is intended to emphasize individual actions and behaviors.
- BBS programs can lead to erroneous reporting. Due to the structure of the program, which rewards "good" conduct, accidents and injuries may go unreported. Nobody desires to be the one to end the "days without injury". When things go awry or unsafe behavior is observed, employees are also averse to investigations and in-depth conversations.
- BBS programs frequently identify the incorrect "root cause". BBS necessitates incident investigations when unsafe behaviors are observed or injuries occur. But frequently, these investigations focus on what occurred rather than the underlying cause or why it occurred.

5. BBS: IMPORTANT CONSIDERATIONS

BBS is not something that can be gradually implemented. Effective implementation requires meticulous planning, long-term commitment, and organization-wide support. How should one then proceed?

According to EHS Today, the six most common errors made by businesses when implementing a BBS program entail the following (Gould, 2019):

- Believing that participation and observation are the foundations of BBS.
- Failing to utilize positive reinforcement effectively and systematically.
- Only changing hourly employees.
- Making safety based on employee behavior the principal responsibility of employees.
- Not training managers, administrators, and hourly workers on the fundamental principles of behavior-change technology.
- Attempting to implement an activity-based "program" within the organization.

6. OBSTACLES THAT EMPEDE BBS EFFECTIVENESS

The development of a safety culture progresses from fundamental principles to fundamental values through the dedication of top-level management, ultimately leading to the realization of the advantages of BBS. Many businesses engage in thorough preparation of safety culture interventions, yet struggle to sustain them as enduring modifications due to insufficient attention to organizational variables. The issues identified by Lal (2023) include managers who persist in adhering to a culture of dependence on safety, a lack of motivation among lower-level workers to engage in mentally stimulating activities, insufficient support from relevant heads of departments and managers, and inadequate capacity to mobilize and engage all employees and associates.

To promote safe practices, it is recommended to implement measures such as modifying behavior, establishing structured infrastructure, monitoring and enforcing safety protocols, providing training and education, and utilizing positive and negative reinforcement techniques. Efficient implementation of safety measures can be achieved when it is considered a line-of-duty responsibility and integrated into daily activities. During regular meetings, it is recommended that the management team engage in

discussions pertaining to safety metrics in addition to other operational parameters. The successful execution of any project necessitates the unwavering commitment and active participation of top-level management. In the absence of such involvement, the desired outcomes of such projects may not be realized (CPCL, 2021).

In order to establish a safe work environment, it is imperative to cultivate a fundamental need for safety practices, including the utilization of personal protective equipment (PPE) by all personnel, from the highest level of management to the lowest level of employees. It is essential that all individuals are cognizant of the safety policy and that top management is actively involved in all safety-related activities. Training is a crucial component in developing a safety culture, and it is recommended that at least 3% of man-hours be allocated to employee training.

The commitment of top management is an essential prerequisite for any action to be taken. The implementation of monitoring as a boardroom practice requires a dedicated commitment from management. The sustainability of a positive safety culture is contingent upon its integration into the boardroom and the level of discourse it receives therein. The efficacy of the system is contingent upon its integration into habitual behavior, which must be sustained over an extended period to effect lasting change. The reason for its failure can be attributed to the absence of a clear corporate vision or policy (Kaila, 2022, and 2022a).

One of the reasons businesses fail to maintain a positive safety culture is attributed to human error or organizational politics; this is often due to underlying conflicts and collective faults within the organization, which can impede the implementation of effective safety measures. BBS aims to address and resolve organizational concerns in tandem, with the goal of cultivating a positive work environment. The acquisition of knowledge and skills by employees through training is contingent upon their active engagement in the learning process, assimilation of information, and practical application of the acquired knowledge. According to Tata Steel (2021), achieving success in safety culture is not a static objective, but rather a dynamic process characterized by fluctuations and variations.

7. CONCLUSION AND RECOMMENDATIONS

Due to the challenges associated with long-term commitment, many businesses perceive the adoption of safety measures as a means of preserving their reputation. Consequently, they execute their assigned tasks and subsequently adopt a passive stance, anticipating unforeseen incidents. Certain enterprises have initiated a safety culture intervention but failed to follow through due to their predominant focus on individual behaviors rather than organizational behaviors. The exchange of ideas and perspectives at various levels within an organization pertaining to topics such as incentives, interpersonal connections, attitudes, and obstacles is believed to generate a novel model of organizational conduct, commonly known as BBS. BBS has evolved from a narrow emphasis on injury reduction (which, regrettably, involves victim blaming) to a comprehensive approach that considers not only behaviors but also the work environment, cultural factors, systems, and employee attitudes; this approach aims to enhance organizational cultures, values, and performance (Johnson, 2021).

The development of a favorable safety culture is a gradual process that necessitates ongoing scrutiny of its sustainability over an extended period. According to Wong et al. (2021), in order to effectively promote a culture of safety and encourage individuals to prioritize it, it is essential for management to consistently evaluate and analyze their strategies while implementing diverse interventions. ISO 45001:2018 (SEIL, 2023) stipulates that risk assessment should encompass human competence and behavioral factors, which should be regarded as internal concerns for risk management.

BBS implementation in the workplace involves careful planning, participation, and commitment from all levels of the business. Here are a few suggestions for a smooth implementation:

- **Leadership Commitment:** Obtain senior management's commitment to prioritizing and supporting BBS efforts. Leaders must establish a clear vision for safety, allocate the required resources, and actively participate in BBS activities.
- **Employee Involvement:** Ensure that employees at all levels are involved in the BBS process. Seek their feedback, invite them to join safety committees or teams, and empower them to take responsibility for safety projects.
- **Training and Education:** Educate employees on BBS principles, safe work practices, danger identification, and the importance of their conduct in maintaining a safe workplace. Refresher courses and continuous education should be used to reinforce this training on a regular basis.
- **Observation and Feedback:** Create a method for observing and recording employee behaviors. Supervisors and designated observers should be trained to perform non-punitive observations, provide constructive criticism, and accurately document observations. Maintain confidentiality while emphasizing the importance of observations as a tool for progress.
- **Conduct Analysis:** Examine the collected data for trends, patterns, and the underlying causes of risky conduct. Utilize this data to prioritize specific behaviors for change and create tailored interventions.
- **Metrics and Goal Setting:** Establish measurable targets for corporate and individual safety performance. Define key performance indicators (KPIs) to monitor progress and assess the effectiveness of BBS activities. Employees should be kept up to date on progress, and milestones should be celebrated on a regular basis.
- **Reinforcement and Recognition:** Use a positive reinforcement system to identify and reward safe actions. To promote safe behaviors and encourage employees to participate actively, use a combination of verbal recognition, incentives, awards, and public gratitude.
- **Constant review and Improvement:** BBS is a continual process that necessitates continuing review and improvement. Review the efficacy of BBS initiatives on a regular basis, elicit employee input, and make appropriate program improvements.
- **Safety Culture Integration:** BBS should be integrated into the organization's broader safety culture. Align BBS with existing safety initiatives, rules and procedures, and foster a culture of shared responsibility for safety.
- **Communication and Engagement:** Create effective communication channels to keep employees up to date on BBS operations, progress, and results. Encourage open communication, create chances for input, and include employees in safety decision-making processes.

By many accounts, successful BBS installation takes time, effort, and a commitment to ongoing improvement. To accomplish long-term improvements in workplace safety, a supportive organizational culture, active employee participation, and continued leadership involvement are required.

REFERENCES

- CPCL (2021). CPCL kickstarts behavior-based safety in refineries in Chennai. Retrieved from: <https://cpcl.co.in/events-updates/cpcl-kickstarts-behaviour-based-safety-in-refinery-at-chennai/>
- Gould, G. (2019, March 7). The pros and cons of behavior-based safety (BBS). Health, Compliance, ESG. Retrieved from: <https://www.wolterskluwer.com/en/expert-insights/the-pros-and-cons-of-behaviorbased-safety-bbs>
- Health and Safety Executive (2023): Human factors: managing human failures. Retrieved from: <https://www.hse.gov.uk/humanfactors/topics/humanfail.htm>

- Johnson, Dave (2021, July 6). Breathing new life into behavior-based safety (BBS) programs. Retrieved from: <https://www.ishn.com/articles/113027-breathing-new-life-into-behavior-based-safety-bbs-programs>
- Kaila, Harbans Lal (2022). Long-term safety culture implementation Prints Publications, New Delhi. ISBN-13: 9788192769462. Retrieved from: <https://www.printspublications.com/book/long-term-safety>
- Kaila, Harbans Lal (2022a). Retrieved from: <https://store.pothi.com/book/ebook-dr-harbans-lal-kaila-behaviour-based-safety-2-0/>
- Lal, H. (2023). Strengthening a positive safety culture despite underlying fear and peer pressure World Safety Journal, XXXII (1), 57–64. Retrieved from: <https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.7770080>
- Safety Culture (2023, March 31). Behavior Based Safety (BBS). Retrieved from: <https://safetyculture.com/topics/behavior-based-safety/>
- SEIL (2023). Behavior-Based Safety (BBS) is implemented at SEIL. Retrieved from: <https://www.seilcorpenergyindia.com/CSR/BBS>
- Tata Steel (2021, March 15) Risk Profiling Turns Deep Shop Floor Experience into Enthusiastic Risk-Based Decision Making. Retrieved from: <https://www.consultdss.com/content-hub/risk-profiling-risk-based-decision-making/>
- Wong SY, Fu ACL, Han J, Lin J, and Lau MC (2021): Effectiveness of customized safety intervention programs to increase the safety culture of hospital staff BMJ Open Qual. 10(4):e000962. DOI: 10.1136/bmjopen-2020-000962. PMID: 34625426; PMCID: PMC8504354.

AUTHORS

Dr. Harbans LAL earned a Master's degree in Psychology from Guru Nanak Dev University and a Ph.D. from Tata Institute of Social Sciences, Mumbai, India. He has been at SNDT Women's University and the Central Labor Institute, Mumbai, for over 28 years. He represented India at Conferences in New York, Berlin, Muscat, Rome, New Zealand, Japan, London, Dubai, Cairo, and Sydney. He is the Editor of the Journal of Psychosocial Research, and serves as Director of the Forum of Behavioral Safety. He has conducted over 1000 behavioral safety programs for the industry.

Prof. Dr. Elias M. CHOUEIRI has been very active in academic and research settings for over 35 years. He is the author/co-author of over 20 books and booklets, and hundreds of refereed publications, technical reports, conference presentations and newspaper articles. He has won more than 20 awards for his scholarship, and has held faculty and managerial positions at several public and private institutions in Lebanon and the USA. He is a member of the WSO Board of Directors, and serves as WSO Liaison Officer to the United Countries. Besides, he assumes the roles of Director of the WSO National Office for Lebanon, Chairperson of the WSO Highway Transportation Committee, and Chairperson of the WSO Transportation of Dangerous Goods Committee.